

Electrochemical Behaviour of Dichromate Ions in Various Base Electrolytes at Dropping Mercury Electrode

B. K. GUPTA, D. S. JAIN and J. N. GAUR

Chemical Laboratories, Rajasthan University, Jaipur 302004

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The present investigations deal with the polarographic behaviour of dichromate ions in different base electrolytes. Solutions containing 1mM of dichromate ions in 0.1M base electrolytes were polarographed at 30°C. The plots of i_d vs \sqrt{h} and i_d vs C (concentration of dichromate ions) were linear and passing through origin for all the cases, reveals that the reductions are diffusion controlled. The plots of $\log i/i_d - i$ vs $E_{d.e.}$ (-V vs S.C.E.) were linear in all systems, but the value of slope was much higher than required for 3 electron reversible reduction (20 mV). These results show the irreversibility of the electrode reaction. The electrode kinetics was studied by Koutecky's method for irreversible electrode process. The kinetic parameters for reduction of dichromate ions in all cases have been calculated. The analytical importance of the results obtained have been discussed.

THE reduction of dichromate ions at d.m.e. has not been studied in detail. Milyaeva¹ studied the reduction of dichromate ions in 6N HCl medium using rotating platinum electrode. Dick² carried out the titration between chromate and dichromate for identification of dichromate in presence of chromate. Seiji³ studied the reduction of dichromate ions using mercury pool under a controlled potential. However, it has been revealed from literature that the electrode kinetics for a reduction of dichromate ions in various base electrolytes have not been studied so far. The present paper deals with the reduction of dichromate ions at d.m.e. in various base electrolytes from analytical aspect. Similar studies on the reduction of chromate, bromate and iodate ions have been reported earlier⁴⁻⁶.

Experimental

Stock solutions of potassium dichromate (0.01M) and other base electrolytes (1.0M) were prepared by dissolving required weight of reagent grade $K_2Cr_2O_7$ and base electrolytes in doubly distilled water. Solutions containing 1 mM dichromate and 0.1M of various base electrolytes were prepared in 25 ml volumetric pyrex flasks. Solutions were also prepared having different dichromate ion concentration in same concentration of base electrolytes. The current voltage (C-V) curves were obtained by manual polarographic set up. The dropping mercury electrode having: $m = 1.1464$ mg/sec. and $t = 3.5$ sec. (at 35 cm of mercury pressure in 0.1M NaOH with applied potential of -1.0 V vs S.C.E.) was used for this purpose. All the experiments were performed at 30°C, which was kept constant with a Haake type ultra thermostat. The solutions were

freed from dissolved oxygen by bubbling purified nitrogen gas for 25 min. The I.R. drop correction was applied wherever needed. For this purpose L.P. conduscope was used.

Results and Discussion

C-V curves were obtained in different base electrolytes. In each case, two waves were obtained except in alkaline media. The first wave has been found to be very small and ill defined, so that it is not useful for analytical purpose. However, second reduction wave was found to be well defined. All the discussions correspond to observation on second

reduction wave. The plots of i_d vs \sqrt{h} were linear and pass through origin for all solutions, showing that the limiting current is governed by diffusion. The same results were obtained by the plots of i_d vs dichromate ions concentration, which were linear and pass through origin. The plots of $\log i/i_d - i$ vs $E_{d.e.}$ (-V vs S.C.E.) were again linear for all the solutions and slopes of these plots were much higher than required for 3 electron reversible reductions of Cr(IV) (20 mM), showing that the reductions are irreversible. The diffusion coefficient of dichromate ions in all base electrolytes have been calculated by Ilkovic equation. The kinetic parameters were calculated by Koutecky's⁷ method in each system. The values of K_f° were obtained by plotting; the graph between $-\log K_f^\circ$ vs E (-V vs N.H.E.) and extrapolated it to zero volt, whereas the slope of these plots gave the value of an . As the standard potential is not known for each system, the value of standard rate constant K_s° could not be calculated. The value of pH was measured after the experiment of each solution and reported in tables.

(i)(a): Effect of concentration of $Cr_2O_7^{-2}$ ions in presence of 0.1M NaOH and 0.1M NaCl :

By increasing the dichromate ion concentration in alkaline media (0.1M NaOH) and in neutral media (0.1M NaCl), the diffusion current increases and half wave potential almost remains the same. The i_d/C comes to constant, showing that the limiting current is diffusion limited. This was also confirmed by a graph between i_d vs C which results into a straight line which pass through origin. The polarographic characteristics are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION OF DICHROMATE IONS ON POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS

	concentration (mM)	i_d (μA)	$E_{1/2}$ ($-V$ vs S.C.E.)	slope (mV)	i_d/C
In 0.1M NaOH	0.5	8.10	1.07	140	16.20
	1.0	16.00	1.07	145	15.95
	1.5	24.24	1.08	150	16.15
	2.0	32.46	1.075	145	16.23
In 0.1M NaCl	0.5	4.90	1.103	120	9.80
	1.0	9.90	1.100	130	9.90
	1.5	14.90	1.110	145	9.90
	2.0	20.00	1.100	160	10.00

(b) Effect of height of mercury reservoir :

In presence of 0.1M NaOH and 0.1M NaCl, by increasing the height, i_d increases and the half wave potential almost remains unchanged. The plots of i_d vs \sqrt{h} were linear and pass through origin, showing that the reduction is diffusion controlled. The value of i_d/\sqrt{h} was found to be constant. The results are summarised in Table 2.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF MERCURY RESERVOIR HEIGHT ON THE POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF DICHROMATE IONS

	Height (cm.)	i_d (μA)	$E_{1/2}$ ($-V$ vs S.C.E.)	slope (mV)	i_d/\sqrt{h}
In 0.1M NaOH	35	16.00	1.070	145	2.70
	40	17.37	1.072	145	2.75
	45	18.07	1.075	150	2.70
In 0.1M NaCl	35	9.90	1.100	130	1.77
	40	11.14	1.105	140	1.77
	45	12.08	1.105	145	1.80

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF DICHROMATE IONS

	Temperature ($^{\circ}C$)	i_d (μA)	$E_{1/2}$ ($-V$ vs S.C.E.)	slope (mV)
In 0.1M NaOH	30	16.00	1.070	145
	35	19.35	1.080	155
	40	20.01	1.085	160
In 0.1M NaCl	30	10.25	1.100	130
	35	10.39	1.102	140
	40	10.76	1.105	160

(c) Effect of temperature :

The polarograms for 1 mM dichromate ions in presence of 0.1M NaOH and 0.1M NaCl were taken at three different temperatures. For both the electrolytes, diffusion current increases by increasing the temperature. The value of slopes of the plots between $\log i/i_d - i$ vs $E_{d.e}$ also slightly increases with rise of temperature, showing that the irreversibility of the electrode process increases with increasing the temperature. The results are summarised in Table 3.

(ii) Effect of alkali metal chlorides :

In presence of different alkali metal chlorides (LiCl to CsCl), i_d increases and half-wave potential shifted to more positive value. This may be due to the increase in size of the cation. The electrode process was again found to be irreversible and the kinetic parameters have been calculated by Koutecky's method. The polarographic characteristics and kinetic parameters have been incorporated in Table 4.

(iii) Effect of sodium halides on the polarographic characteristics of the $Cr_2O_7^{-2}$ ions :

In presence of different sodium halides solution, i_d decreases (except in sodium iodide) and half-wave potential shifted to more positive value. This may be due to the change in the size of the anion. The reduction is again irreversible. The kinetic parameters are calculated by Koutecky's method. The polarographic characteristics and kinetic parameters are recorded in Table 5.

(iv) Effect of sodium salts of different organic acids on the reduction of $Cr_2O_7^{-2}$ ions :

The reduction has been carried out in presence of sodium salts of various organic acids. In each case, the reduction was diffusion controlled but irreversible. The kinetic parameters were again obtained by Koutecky's method. The results are summarised in Table 6.

(v) Reduction of $Cr_2O_7^{-2}$ ions in presence of various oxy-anions :

The reduction of dichromate ions was studied in presence of selenate, selenite, tungstate, molybdate, and arsenite etc. In each case, well defined irreversible reduction wave was obtained. The kinetic parameters were calculated by Koutecky's method. The results are tabulated in Table 7.

(vi) Reduction of $Cr_2O_7^{-2}$ ions in presence of various base electrolytes :

The reduction of 1 mM dichromate ions have been studied in presence of $MgCl_2$, $LiClO_4$, $NaClO_4$, $Na_2S_2O_3$, Na_2SO_4 and NaOH. The reduction was found to be diffusion controlled and irreversible in each case. The polarographic characteristics and kinetic parameters are incorporated in Table 8.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF ALKALI METAL HALIDES ON THE REDUCTION OF DICHROMATE IONS

Sl. No.	Supporting electrolytes (0.1M)	pH	i_d (μA)	$E_{1/2}$ (-V vs S.C.E.)	slope (mV)	$D^{\ddagger} \times 10^3$ (cm ² /sec.)	K_{fh}° (cm/sec.)	an
1.	NH ₄ Cl	7.0	17.56	1.605	150	3.56	7.94×10^{-10}	0.37
2.	LiCl	6.0	7.73	1.185	130	1.61	6.31×10^{-9}	0.43
3.	NaCl	6.0	9.62	1.100	130	1.95	6.04×10^{-10}	0.45
4.	KCl	6.3	10.20	1.075	125	2.07	2.51×10^{-9}	0.46
5.	RbCl	7.0	10.76	1.045	120	2.18	3.63×10^{-9}	0.48
6.	CsCl	7.0	10.39	0.970	130	2.10	6.31×10^{-8}	0.49

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF SODIUM HALIDES ON THE POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS OF DICHROMATE IONS

Sl. No.	Supporting electrolytes (0.1M)	pH	i_d (μA)	$E_{1/2}$ (-V vs S.C.E.)	slope (mV)	$D^{\ddagger} \times 10^3$ (cm ² /sec.)	K_{fh}° (cm/sec.)	an
1.	NaF	6.1	10.00	1.105	115	2.03	1.00×10^{-11}	0.60
2.	NaCl	6.0	9.62	1.100	130	1.95	6.04×10^{-10}	0.45
3.	NaBr	6.0	0.06	1.085	135	1.94	5.01×10^{-10}	0.54
4.	NaI	6.6	10.00	1.080	140	2.03	2.51×10^{-9}	0.48

TABLE 6—EFFECT OF SODIUM SALTS OF DIFFERENT ORGANIC ACIDS ON THE REDUCTION OF DICHROMATE IONS

Sl. No.	Supporting electrolytes (0.1M)	pH	i_d (μA)	$E_{1/2}$ (-V vs S.C.E.)	slope (mV)	$D^{\ddagger} \times 10^3$ (cm ² /sec.)	K_{fh}° (cm/sec.)	an
1.	Sod. formate	7.6	10.20	1.130	107	2.07	6.31×10^{-10}	0.54
2.	Sod. acetate	6.0	9.25	1.082	115	1.87	3.16×10^{-10}	0.54
3.	Sod. citrate	7.9	7.92	1.097	110	1.61	1.99×10^{-10}	0.51
4.	Sod. malonate	8.0	9.81	0.970	120	1.99	1.58×10^{-10}	0.60
5.	Sod. salicylate	7.4	11.15	1.105	130	2.26	3.98×10^{-9}	0.46

TABLE 7—EFFECT OF VARIOUS OXY-ANIONS ON THE REDUCTION OF DICHROMATE IONS

Sl. No.	Base electrolyte (0.1M)	pH	i_d (μA)	$E_{1/2}$ (-V vs S.C.E.)	slope (mV)	$D^{\ddagger} \times 10^3$ (cm ² /sec.)	K_{fh}° (cm/sec.)	an
1.	Sod. selenite	8.0	11.80	1.270	165	2.39	4.16×10^{-8}	0.33
2.	Sod. selenate	8.7	8.30	1.255	120	1.68	5.62×10^{-10}	0.45
3.	Sod. tungstate	8.1	10.86	1.330	130	2.20	5.01×10^{-11}	0.49
4.	Sod. molybdate	7.2	10.00	1.335	150	2.03	6.31×10^{-9}	0.36
5.	Sod. arsenite	10.3	6.60	1.265	330	1.34	2.81×10^{-11}	0.46

TABLE 8—EFFECT OF VARIOUS BASE ELECTROLYTES ON REDUCTION OF DICHROMATE IONS

Sl. No.	Base electrolyte (0.1M)	pH	i_d (μA)	$E_{1/2}$ (-V vs S.C.E.)	slope (mV)	$D^{\ddagger} \times 10^3$ (cm ² /sec.)	K_{fh}° (cm/sec.)	an
1.	MgCl ₂	5.6	7.17	0.780	220	1.45	6.60×10^{-5}	0.27
2.	LiClO ₄	8.0	5.16	1.020	170	1.05	5.01×10^{-7}	0.35
3.	NaClO ₄	6.59	9.25	0.985	175	1.87	1.99×10^{-11}	0.55
4.	Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃	7.2	8.49	1.020	140	1.72	1.00×10^{-11}	0.47
5.	Na ₂ SO ₃	8.6	7.55	1.025	150	1.53	7.94×10^{-9}	0.51
6.	Na ₂ SO ₄	9.1	4.25	1.030	160	1.87	1.99×10^{-9}	0.46
7.	NaOH	12.10	16.04	1.070	145	3.23	7.07×10^{-9}	0.46

As the reduction of dichromate ions is diffusion controlled in presence of various oxy-anions, different carboxylates, various types of alkali and alkaline earth metal chlorides, sodium halides and various other base electrolytes, this provides a useful method for determination of dichromate ions in presence of these indifferent electrolytes. Even a hundred fold excess of these indifferent electrolytes do not interfere with the determination of dichromate ions at d.m.e.

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